

Accession Number: P270540

11 feb 2016

Patient ID: P16776

Optima CT660

Exam Description: TERMO-ABLAZIONE TC GUI

Report Dose

Series	Type	Scan Range (mm)	CTDIvol (mGy)	DLP (mGy-cm)	Phantom cm
1	Scout	-	-	-	-
2	Helical	I169.000-I336.500	4.75	110.16	Body 32
3	Helical	I234.000-I260.250	4.49	32.55	Body 32
4	Helical	I234.000-I260.250	4.45	32.21	Body 32
5	Helical	I234.000-I260.250	4.48	32.48	Body 32
6	Helical	I234.000-I260.250	4.49	32.51	Body 32
7	Helical	I234.000-I260.250	4.51	32.65	Body 32
8	Helical	I234.000-I260.250	4.46	32.31	Body 32
9	Helical	I234.000-I260.250	4.46	32.34	Body 32
Total Exam DLP:				337.21	